

BASIC PRINCIPLES AND PROCEDURE FOR STUDYING CAUSATIVE CONSTRUCTIONS IN MODERN LINGUISTICS

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Abstract: In this paper, we set the task of a comprehensive, complex study of causative constructions in the Uzbek language. The system-structural approach to the study of the grammatical structure in recent years has been actively supplemented by the functional-semantic aspect. At the present stage of linguistic research, it is necessary to pay attention to the multidimensional study of the language. There is no doubt that the rich history of the study of the Uzbek language paved the way for its multifaceted study.

Key words: morphological level, categories of the language, linguistics, category of causation.

As the history of the study of the category in the Uzbek language shows, causation has never been one of the basic categories of the language, such as the categories of voice, modality, aspectuality, time, the place and meaning of which has long been recognized and quite fully studied. However, the existence of causative relations in language is obvious and beyond doubt. Causativity is a category that determines the causal relationships existing in the human mind. Causativity can be called one of the most understudied and “misunderstood” categories of language.

The heyday of its study falls on the 60s of the twentieth century, when it was actively studied and the grammatical system of the Uzbek language, however, causation practically did not find its place in this system. The stormy study of the system of the Uzbek language in the second half of the 20th century practically did not affect the category of causation. One gets the feeling that the existence of this category in the language is not noticed or is simply ignored. Until recently, causation was not recognized either in the semantics or in the grammar of the Uzbek language.

Today we can say that causation as a category has no specific place in the system of the Uzbek language, although, as we have already said, it is a category that is present in almost any developed language of the world, since it has a rather important conceptual content inherent in human consciousness. And the fact that it has not yet found its due reflection in Uzbek linguistics and, moreover, has not found its place in the language system, seems at least strange and undeserved.

The category of causation is interesting primarily because its semantics is reflected in different languages in different ways. In the Uzbek language, the category of causation receives clear grammatical features. As is known, the highest manifestation of any semantic category in a particular language is contained in its grammatical structure.

Causativity, first of all, is considered from the standpoint of the functional-semantic approach. Functional-semantic categories are those that have a branched system of means of expression related to different levels of the language. In the Uzbek language, causation is realized at all language levels. Thus, the lexical level is associated with the lexical means of expression. The basic unit of this level is lexical causatives. The morphological level implies the presence of

morphological (word-forming) means of expression. The basic unit is the morphological causative. The syntactic level is associated with the syntactic means of expression, which are represented by analytic causatives.

Causativity is a category that expresses a causal relationship between two events, while the occurrence of one event is associated with the impact of another event, i.e. has a chain character. We call causative verbs verbs denoting effects on objects. These influences cause response actions, states of caused objects.

The relevant features of causative verbs include:

- 1) semantic sign - impact on objects;
- 2) the presence of a non-causative corlyata;
- 3) semantic transitivity.

Thus, we call a causative verb a verb denoting an impact on an object in order to change its state or induce it to perform an action, and having a correlative non-causative correlate that expresses the action, state or quality that occurs as a result of the impact.

When analyzing the causative constructions of the Uzbek language, we consider it important to single out the continuum scale, the semantic types of causation. In this case, the analysis is carried out taking into account the situations formed by the causative verb. Depending on the ability to form this or that situation, causative verbs are subdivided into semantic types. Based on the material of the Uzbek language, we study both factitive and permissive, contact and distant causative constructions traditionally identified in linguistics, as well as types of social causation that have not been sufficiently developed in linguistics. Constructions with social causatives denoting joint action, assistivity and supervision are studied. All types of causation are considered from the point of view of semantics, grammar and functional features.

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